

A National Response to Global Challenge: The Importance of Establishing a National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and IDPs

Mina Margaret Ogbanga
Rivers State University
mina.ogbanga@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

Returnees have not been properly taken care of because the NCFRMI have not been fully operational. There are other bodies in the country like NEMA and SEMA performing the same function, and it becomes difficult for returnees, especially those in camps to know which officials are catering for them given the overlapping IDPs and returnees management agencies. In Nigeria, returnees are facing emotional and social stress. Most of the returnees are stigmatized by their fellow citizens, and this is damaging psychologically. The intentions of government in helping returnees to be reintegrated into society have not worked very well due to the corrupt and insincere attitude of government and NCFRMI officials. The present paper is on the importance for the creation of national commission for refugees, migrants, internally displaced persons (NCFRMI)

Introduction

In Nigeria, the number of migrants is on the increase as a result of political instability and unemployment. Of the total figure of migrants, the assessment indicates that 13.33 percent were poor due to income inequality, 0.99 percent by lack of opportunities, and 85.68 percent as a result of unemployment (Isaac, 2016). According to Jibole (2016) there are over 2,241,484 migrants as of February, 2016. According to the report, this figure is particularly based on an assessment conducted from November to December 2015 by the international organization for migrations (IOM) Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) team in 207 local Government Areas (LGA) covering 13 states of Nigeria. In fact, as migrants are returning to their habitual residence, other are still migrating, thereby making it difficult to accurately have reliable statistics of migrants in Nigeria. Since 2011, the population of the south-south, south-east of Nigeria states has been affected by constant migration (UNICEF, 2016). Thus, the government took a step in curbing migration, and having accurate data of citizens leaving the country in search of greener pastures, and so the national commission for refugees, migrants, and internally displaced persons (NCFRMI) was formed to counsel and reintegrate returnees from abroad into the Nigerian society, given the harsh conditions suffered in countries like Indonesia, Malaysia, Libya.

However, the agency has not been able to properly perform its statutory function of counseling and reintegrating returnees into the Nigerian society. This is because of these challenges; the porous nature of the Nigerian borders, the absence of the agency in some states of the federation, undocumented data of returnees, less manpower and poor funding from the government. This has made the agency to function poorly in terms of reintegrating returnees, sadly, returnees have had to deal with hard conditions in internally Displaced persons (IDPs) camps. Some of these returnees situated in IDP camps are attacked, resulting to rape and loss of lives, given the fact that the NCFRMI is unable to provide accommodations and adequate security, and so sought IDP camps as the last resort. Some that have lost their means of livelihood and source of income, even find it difficult to feed in such camps where foods are in short supply. Furthermore, returnees to Nigeria face social stigmatization, ethnic and religious discrimination. This makes rehabilitation, reintegration into Nigerian society a colossal impossibility due to governments negligence to tackle political corruption, ethnicity and unemployment, which are precursors for migration from the country in the first place.

National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI),

The National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI), formerly known as the **National Commission for Refugees (NCFR)**, is an agency of the Federal Government of Nigeria, established by Decree 52 of 1989 now Cap. N21, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004 (NCFRMI Act) to manage the affairs of refugees, migrants and internally displaced persons in Nigeria. The agency is one of six agencies under the supervision of the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development. It is headed by a Federal Commissioner.

Origin

The National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons was established by the Federal Government of Nigeria to fulfill the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 319(IV) under Article 35 of the United Nations 1951 Convention. The agency was formerly known for managing only refugee affairs but was later expanded in 2002 by the former President of Nigeria, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo. In 2021, President Muhammadu Buhari appointed Hon. Imaan Sulaiman-Ibrahim as the Federal Commissioner of the agency.¹

Functions of the Commission (NCFRMI) are as follows:

- i. Advise the Federal Government on Policy matters relating to refugees, migrants and internally displaced persons;
- ii. Protect and assist IDPs and seek the collaboration of other MDAs for such protection and assistance;

- iii. Coordinate migration issues, protect migrants and their families, including other Nationals resident in Nigeria, pursuant to the provisions of international conventions, protocols and treaties guiding the protection of rights and promotion of the welfare of migrants;
- iv. Through the Consultative Committee, provide a platform for the uniform administration of migration for formulating, reviewing and implementing a national policy on migration and development;
- v. Work towards eliminating irregular migration and encourage orderly and regular migration of Nigerians;
- vi. In collaboration with relevant agencies of government, ensure compliance with the provisions of the Kampala Convention;
- vii. Support State Governments in the creation and maintenance of an updated register of all IDPs within their jurisdiction;
- viii. Register and make personal documentation of IDPs.
- ix. Identify, mobilize and coordinate refugees, migrants and internally displaced persons' camp management agencies and other sectorial partners, towards ensuring effective co-ordination of other sectors responding to the provision of assistance and needs;
- x. Facilitate the restoration of communities displaced due to ecological induced occurrences;
- xi. Coordinate the activities of all agencies on refugee, migration and internal displacement issues;
- xii. Ensure that internally displaced persons are protected during and after displacement, return or resettlement and reintegration;
- xiii. Develop SOPs, in conjunction with relevant MDAs and inter-governmental or humanitarian agencies to return, re-admit and re-integrate, excluded migrants in line with extant legal instruments to promote the human rights and well-being of migrants;
- xiv. Develop policy framework to encourage and promote voluntary return of IDPs to their respective homes or place of habitual residence or resettle voluntarily in another part of the country with dignity;
- xv. Proffer long lasting solutions to the problems of IDPs through reconstruction and renovation of destroyed homes and properties;
- xvi. Encourage and ensure capacity building and skill acquisition through training programs to Nigerians who are being repatriated in order to be self-dependent and gainfully engaged upon their return;
- xvii. Collaborate with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to negotiate and facilitate the implementation of bilateral agreements with nations repatriating Nigerian citizens;
- xviii. Collaborate with relevant agencies to negotiate the safe return of Nigerian migrants, where the host country has legitimate cause to return them or where they decide to return voluntarily;

- xix. Where there is a large-scale influx of persons claiming to fall within the meaning of refugees under this Act or massive internal displacement or in situations of mass return of deportees, the Commission shall, in consultation with other relevant stakeholders, provide emergency remedial measures and advise the Federal Government on the appropriate measures to be taken.

Methodology

Study Design

A research design means the entire procedure employed to bring together different components of a study in a lucid and logical way, thereby making sure that the research problem is handled adequately. The design carries the blueprint for the collection, measurement and dissection of data. For this reason, the study adopts the survey design. The imperative of this design is to interrogate respondents on the topic of discourse and then analyse their responses. This is done through the use of questionnaire.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is centred on displaced persons, returnees in camps in Mbiama, Akinima, Akiniso and Abua of Rivers State.

Sources of Data

The data used for the study are from two sources: the primary and secondary. The primary sources are; questionnaire and interviews, while for that of the secondary sources are; government journals, articles, the internet, etc.

Sample Size

A sample is a subset of a population that is used to represent the entire population. In doing a research, it is practically not feasible to survey every member of the study population because it can create ambiguity and obscure the objectivity of the study, given the large number of the population. In order to avoid these things, the researcher chooses a smaller number of respondents. If the sample chosen truly represents the larger group, the researcher can draw a generalisation. In view of this, the study will use 100 respondents out of the entire population in the study area. These 100 respondents are internally displaced persons, returnees living in camps in Mbiama, Akinima, Abuoha, Akiniso. It is believed that the views of these 100

respondents will represent the general view of the people in camps since everyone cannot be sampled.

Sampling Technique

A sampling technique is used in drawing samples from a population usually in a way that the sample will facilitate and accommodate the general view of the population on a particular topic. A sample technique is a pattern used in determining samples vital for particular studies. In Social Science researches, there are two types of sampling techniques: probability and non-probability sampling techniques. The probability sampling technique uses randomization to select sample members. This type of sampling technique allows every member of the study population to have an equal chance of participating in the study. The non-probability sampling technique uses non-random technique. This type is basically reliant on the judgement of the researcher, and it is restricted to individuals the researcher decides to include in the study. There are subsets of the probability sampling, and they are: Simple Random Sampling (SRS), stratified sampling, cluster sampling, systematic sampling and multistage sampling. For the non-probability sampling, the subsets are: convenience sampling, haphazard sampling, purposive sampling, quota sampling, snowball sampling, etc. For this study, the simple random sampling technique is ideal since it deals with randomization of respondents in an independent and all-inclusive way. The sampling frame form consists of community leaders, youths, students and business people from which the respondents will be randomly selected.

Methods of Data Collection

Data collected for this study are from questionnaire, interviews, the internet and articles. These methods provided invaluable information for the researcher.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected are analyzed in line with the research objectives. These responses collected from the respondents are measured in frequency and percentage tables.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Marital Status of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Marital Status		
Single	108	60
Married	22	12.2
Divorced	20	11.1
Widowed	30	16.7
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 1 on marital status of respondents, single accounted for

108(60%), married accounted for 22(12.2%), divorced accounted for 20(11.1%), widowed accounted for 30(16.7%) of respondents used for the study.

Table 2: Educational Qualification of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Educational Qualification		
Primary	83	46.1
Secondary	69	38.3
Tertiary	28	15.5
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 2 on educational qualification of respondents, primary accounted for 83(46.1%), secondary accounted for 69(38.3%), tertiary accounted for 28(15.5%) of respondents used for the study.

Data Analysis

Table 3: The National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons was created to protect refugees, asylum seekers and IDPS?

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	84	46.7
Agree	68	37.8
Strongly disagree	17	9.4
Disagree	11	6.1
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 3 on the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons was created to protect refugees, asylum seekers and IDPS, strongly agree accounted for 84(46.7%), agree accounted for 68(37.8%), strongly disagree accounted for 17(9.4%), disagree accounted for 11(6.1%) of respondents that answered the question.

Table 4: The NCFRMI is responsible for integrating returnees back into the Nigerian society?

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	86	47.8
Agree	66	36.7
Strongly disagree	18	10
Disagree	10	5.5
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 4 on the NCFRMI is responsible for integrating returnees back into the Nigerian society, strongly agree accounted for 86(47.8%), agree accounted for 66(36.7%), strongly disagree accounted for 18(10%), disagree accounted for 10(5.5%) of respondents that answered the question.

Table 5: The NCFRMI is responsible for assisting returnees into the country?

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	101	56.1
Agree	51	28.3
Strongly disagree	16	8.9
Disagree	12	6.7
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 5 on the NCFRMI is responsible for assisting returnees into the country, strongly agree accounted for 101(56.1%), agree accounted for 51(28.3%), strongly disagree accounted for 16(8.9%), disagree accounted for 12(6.7%) of respondents that answered the question.

Table 6: The NCFRMI is responsible for resettling returnees and IDPs.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	89	49.4
Agree	43	23.9
Strongly disagree	34	18.9
Disagree	14	7.8
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2019.

From table 6 on the NCFRMI is responsible for resettling returnees and IDPs, strongly agree accounted for 89(49.4%), agree accounted for 43(23.9%), strongly disagree accounted for 34(18.9%), disagree accounted for 14(7.8%) of respondents that answered the question.

Table 7: Poor funding is a challenge faced by the NCFRMI.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	85	47.2
Agree	47	26.1
Strongly disagree	30	16.7
Disagree	18	10
Total	180	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2018.

From table 4.2.8 on poor funding is a challenge faced by the NCFRMI, strongly agree accounted for 85(47.2%), agree accounted for 47(26.1%), strongly disagree accounted for 30(16.7%), disagree accounted for 18(10%) of respondents that answered the question.

Discussion of Findings

The standard of living of citizens is very poor. Citizens cannot have access to quality road, hospitals, food, sanitation, etc; these anomalies make citizens leave the country. It is not news that Nigerians are finding it difficult to settle in other countries. Some are jailed, put under terrible conditions, and others are deported back to Nigeria. In order to help, support and reintegrate these returnees into Nigeria, the Federal Government created the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI). This body was to assist the returnees settle well into the country by giving them psychological and financial support. From the responses of respondents, the study discovered that the NCFRMI has not been carrying out its functions. According to the respondents, the body in charge of taking care of them are facing poor funding. Aside poor funding, corruption within the agency is another burden. Most of the finance given by the government and individuals are not used in meeting the needs of the returnees settled in camps. It is pertinent to point out that some of the officials of the NCFRMI decried overlapping IDPs agencies. For them, they are not totally functional because there are other agencies like the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) doing the same job. This overlapping function is really troubling according to the officials. Lastly, the study found out that despite the various agencies, including NCFRMI, created to take care of returnees, these persons settled in camps still suffer in the hands of rapists, criminals, who enter into these camps and carry out their activities freely. The respondents within these camps decry lack of security presence, and this is a big challenge for them. For other returnees, they complained of the stigmatization they are facing in the hands of other citizens.

Summary and Conclusion

The ultimate desire of every returnee into Nigeria is to relocate back to him or her community of origin, pick up the broken pieces of their lives and rebuild their means of livelihood. As Nigeria intensifies the battle against insecurity, unemployment and poor standard of living, agencies were created to help returnees fully incorporate into their own country they left due to insecurity, unemployment and poor living conditions. Consequently, the National Commission For Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons was created. The body was tasked with the responsibility of assisting returnees settle in. the body was to help returnees in the provision of food and shelter psychological and social support. Sadly, the NCFRMI has not been able to totally perform its functions. The body is challenged by poor funding. This is because the government has so much to cater for, and it is taking a toll on the function of the NCFRMI. Another serious anomaly that has inhabited the function for the NCFRMI is corruption. The body usually diverts funds meant for the rehabilitation and support of the returnees and internally displaced persons. Returnees have not been properly taken care of because the NCFRMI have not been fully operational. There are other bodies in the country like NEMA and SEMA performing the same function, and it becomes difficult for returnees, especially those in camps to know which officials are catering for them given the overlapping IDPs and returnees management agencies. In Nigeria, returnees are facing emotional and social stress. Most of the returnees are stigmatized by their fellow citizens, and this is damaging psychologically. The intentions of government in helping returnees to be reintegrated into society has not worked very well due to the corrupt and insincere attitude of government and NCFRMI officials.

Recommendations

- (i) The Nigerian state should make effort at addressing the symptom instead of the cause of illegal migration. Consistent deployment of security personnel is only a first aid measure. The long-time solution is good governance with a robust institutional frame work that ensures a prudent and effective management of resources to better the lot of its citizenry.
- (ii) Government at all levels should begin to treat unemployment as serious problem. To pull a plug on unemployment, the government should be intentional in providing quality jobs for the people.
- (iii) There is the need for government to provide basic and quality infrastructure in order for citizen to live comfortably. When these things are in place, citizens would love to stay in the country.
- (iv) There is the need for the Federal Government of Nigeria to have a stricter control of border posts in northern Nigeria so as to avert illegal immigrants from the Maghreh region into the country. This would require the establishment of joint

border patrol between Nigeria, Chad, Niger, Cameroon and Benin republics using heavy surveillance equipment like well equipped helicopters and satellites.

- (v) A strategic collaboration between Government, Non State Actors and Private Sectors in addressing the menace is a strategic step that needs to be taken to sustain these process there needs to be grassroots participation and knowledge to ensure parents and siblings alike know the dangers of these unhealthy adventures such as illegal migration.

References

- Akanji, S. (2012) "The Drivers of Immigration in Contemporary Society: Unequal Distribution of Resources and Opportunities". *Human Ecology*. 35 (6): 775–776. doi: 10.1007/s10745-007-9111-z .
- Akanji, S. (2012) . "The Labor Demand Curve is Downward Sloping: Reexamining the Impact of Immigration on the Labor Market". *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* . 118 (4): 1335–1374.
- Akinirinde, G. and Olukoya, F. (2017). "*On the Corner: Day Labor in Africa*". UCLA Center for the Study of Urban Poverty. Archived from the original (PDF) on 10 October 2017. Retrieved 11 December 2017.
- Anarfi, T. & Piel, R. (2015). "Welfare effects of illegal immigration" (PDF). *Journal of Population Economics* . 22 (1): 131–144. doi : 10.1007/s00148-007-0182-3 .
- Asiedu, M., Anarfi et al, Twum-BaahManuh et al (2016). "Learning to Be Illegal: Undocumented Youth and Shifting Legal Contexts in the Transition " (PDF).
- Awumbbila et al (2017). "Understanding the effects of legalising undocumented immigrants". *Vox EU.org* . Archived from the original on 17 May 2018. Retrieved 16 May 2018.
- Crimes by Illegals are Buried in Amnesty Push" . Archived from the original on 14 July 2014. Retrieved 4 June 2014.
- Derek, F. (2016). "The Unwelcome Return of 'Illegals'. *The New York Times*.
- Die, M.; Asiedu, F. (2016). "Are undocumented immigrants committing a crime? Not necessarily". Archived from the original on 4 July 2018. Retrieved 11 July 2018.
- Dietrich, F. (2015) "*Here's the Reality About Illegal Immigrants in the United States*". Archived from the original on 29 June 2018. Retrieved 18 July 2018.

- Dietrich, G. (2015). *121 murders attributed to illegals released by Obama administration*". The Washington Times. Archived from the original on 11 August 2015. Retrieved 21 August 2015.
- Donald, M. (2017). User Generated Racism: Russia's media and migrants". *The European Journalism Observatory*. Archived from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2018.
- Done, Y. (2017). *Asylum seekers', 'illegal immigrants' and entry without a visa*" . Advisory Guidelines 2011. Australian Press Council. Archived from the original on 1 August 2015. Retrieved 5 May 2014.
- Fayomi, D. (2016). The Economic Contribution of Unauthorized Workers: An Industry Analysis". *Regional Science and Urban Economics* . 67: 119–134.
- Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta, Does Employing Undocumented Workers Give Firms a Competitive Advantage? , November 2012" (PDF). Archived (PDF) from the original on 12 April 2013. Retrieved 8 November 2012.
- Fredrick, L. (2016). "*The Economic Effect of Immigration Policies: Analyzing and Simulating the U.S. Case*" (PDF).
- Hiltner, D. & Stephen, T. (2017). "*Illegal, Undocumented, Unauthorized: The Terms of Immigration Reporting*". The New York Times.
- Iheanacho, F. and Ughaerumba, R. (2015). *Beyond Smoke and Mirrors: Mexican Immigration in an Era of Economic Integration*. Yussell Sage Foundation.
- Isaac, D. (2016). "The labor market effects of reducing the number of illegal immigrants". *Review of Economic Dynamics*. 18 (4): 792– 821. doi : 10.1016/j.red.2015.07.005 .
- Jacklyn, G. (2016). *Missing the Boat?* A paper delivered to 'Reporting on Asylum Seekers and Refugees: A Walkley Media Forum' convened by the Media Entertainment & Arts Alliance, 19 June 2017" (PDF). Proceedings Reporting on Asylum Seekers and Refugees: A Walkley Media Forum, Regatta Hotel, Brisbane, Australia. Queensland University of Technology. Archived (PDF) from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2014. Illegals". 13 December 2011.
- Jennisen, H. (2016). *You Say 'Illegal Alien.' I Say 'Undocumented Immigrant.' Who's Right?*". 18 December 2017.
- Jennissen, H. (2016) "Drop the I-Word Campaign" . Race Forward. 23 September 2013. Archived from the original on 23 February 2014. Retrieved 2 March 2014.

- Joel, P. (2016). "How journalism can rid migration of its sour reputation". *European Journalism Centre*. Archived from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2014.
- Jones, G. (2016) "The State of U.S. Immigration Policy: The Quandary of Economic Methodology and the Relevance of Economic Research to Know". *Journal of Law, Economics and Policy*. 5 (1): 177–193. Archived from the original on 21 December 2009. Retrieved 10 December, 2009.
- Kerion, M. (2016). *Economic Effects of Granting Legal Status and Citizenship to Undocumented Immigrants*". Pew Hispanic Center. Archived (PDF) from the original on 11 December 2016. Retrieved 11 December 2017.
- Tacol, H.I and Okali, C. (2017). "Survey of Migrants, Part One: Attitudes about Immigration and Major Demographic Characteristics". *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*. 34 (12): 2547–2567.
- Tacoli, H. and Okali, C. (2017). "The Impact of Unauthorized Immigrants on the Budgets of State and Local Governments". 6 December 2017. Archived from the original on 22 July 2016. Retrieved 28 June 2017.
- Terrence, S. (2016) "Key Migration Terms". 14 January 2015. Archived from the original on 12 January 2018. Retrieved 11 January 2018.
- West, Z. (2018) " "Illegal Alien" Is One of Many Correct Legal Terms for "Illegal Immigrant". Cato Institute. 14 October 2019. Retrieved 15 October 2019. Words Matter PICUM". Archived from the original on 20 December 2017. Retrieved 11 January 2018.
- Zoomer et al cited in Fayomi, S. (2018). *"Trade, Legal, and Illegal Immigration"* (PDF). University of Westminster. Archived from the original (PDF) on 17 February 2017. Retrieved 12 December 2018.[dubious – discuss] Accessed 11 December 2018.